

dormancy of about 12 wk. It is moderately resistant to sheath blight, brown spot, and stem borer.

The 1984 Annual Rice Workshop

(AICRIP) recommended NC492 as a promising variety for semideep water situations in West Bengal, Bihar, Orissa, and Andhra Pradesh. It has been

recommended for minikit demonstration trials in farmers fields for 2 yr and is in the prerelease stage in West Bengal. *J*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Character association in upland rice cultivars of India

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Ninety-eight local ricecultivars grown in a randomized block design with three replications in July 1983 were assessed

for the association among 11 traits at the genotypic (r_g) and phenotypic (r_p) levels (see table).

In general, genotypic associations were higher than phenotypic, but values of both were either positive or negative. This indicates that r_p is slightly reduced by environmental effects. At both the r_g and r_p levels, yield per plant was positive and significantly associated with days to flowering, leaf angle, leaf length, plant height, panicle length, sheath length,

tillers per plant, and grains per panicle. Yield per plant was associated with test weight only at the r_g level. Tillers per plant and test weight directly contributed to yield. Other auxiliary traits that showed positive association with yield were also positively associated among themselves. Any one of these traits could be utilized as selection criteria for yield improvement in upland rice. *J*

Genotypic (G) and phenotypic (P) associations among 11 traits of upland rices. ^a

Trait		Culm angle	Leaf angle	Leaf length	Plant height	Panicle length	Sheath length	Tillers/plant	Grains/panicle	Test weight	Grain yield/plant
Days to flowering	G	-0.08	0.45**	0.52**	0.53**	0.58**	0.40**	0.05	0.49**	-0.06	0.31**
	P	-0.08	0.41**	0.37**	0.50**	0.48**	0.26**	0.03	0.41**	-0.07	0.20*
Culm angle	G		0.17	0.14	-0.21*	-0.25**	0.11	-0.10	-0.13	0.20*	-0.08
	P		0.17	0.08	-0.17	-0.17	0.05	0.01	-0.05	0.16	0.01
Leaf angle	G			0.42**	0.55**	0.39**	0.45**	0.15	0.55**	0.06	0.36**
	P			0.30**	0.49**	0.32**	0.32**	0.06**	0.43**	0.06	0.20*
Leaf length	G				0.75**	0.67**	0.89**	-0.29**	0.51**	0.19	0.54**
	P				0.58**	0.58**	0.65**	-0.10	0.36**	0.14	0.31**
Plant height	G					0.73**	0.68**	-0.17	0.57**	0.01	0.63**
	P					0.67**	0.52**	-0.07	0.47**	0.10	0.43**
Panicle length	G						0.57**	-0.16	0.51**	-0.10	0.49**
	P						0.45**	-0.05	0.54**	0.20	0.34**
Sheath length	G							-0.24*	0.53**	0.09	0.43**
	P							-0.26	0.37**	0.06	0.27**
Tillers/plant	G								-0.31**	-0.26**	0.20*
	P								0.22*	-0.19*	0.29**
Grains/panicle	G									0.43**	0.26**
	P									-0.37**	0.36**
Test weight	G										0.27**
	P										0.09

^a Significant at 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.

Hot water treatment of rice seed for international shipment

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Hot water treatment to control several seedborne pathogens of rice is a widely used quarantine practice in the international exchange of germplasm. One limitation to its use is potentially

deleterious effects on germination and seedling vigor. The possibility that genotypes may differ substantially in sensitivity to hot water treatment poses serious complications in the interpretation of international testing data.

The effect of different hot water treatments and different posttreatment storage conditions on the seed quality of

four rice cultivars was studied. The cultivars were japonica and indica ecotypes to represent sensitive and resistant responses to hot water treatment. Temperature limits and exposure periods tested encompassed the range of treatment conditions recommended for rice by ASEAN quarantine officials.

Seed quality changes were evaluated

under laboratory and upland field conditions in four replications.

Laboratory tests were performed according to International Seed Testing Association (1976) rules.

Hot water treatment at 52°C for 15 or 30 min or 57°C for 15 min did not damage seed quality when the seed was not presoaked (see table). Hot water at 52°C for 15 min actually improved field seedling vigor. Treatment at 57°C for 30 min significantly reduced seed quality, with further reduction when the seed was presoaked. Water temperature interacts with the length of hot water exposure, affecting viability.

Hot water-treated seed is seldom planted immediately after treatment. To determine whether hot water-treated seed deteriorates more rapidly over time, seed quality was evaluated after storage for 45 d. Seed quality deteriorated after storage under cool conditions (19°C at 50% relative humidity [RH]) and room temperature conditions (24-32°C and 78% RH). Room-stored seed was more severely affected, especially when treated at 57°C for 30 min.

Seed which was not presoaked tended to maintain viability and field emergence performance scores when subjected to regimes of 52°C for 15 and 30 min and 57°C for 15 min (see table). However, presoaked seed maintained viability and field emergence performance only with the 52°C for 15 and for 30 min regimes. The four cultivars followed a similar trend in response to the hot water treatments but showed some differences

Hot water treatment combinations observed to be safe for application to rice seed. IRRI.

	Hot water treatments ^a			
	52°C		57°C	
	15 min	30 min	15 min	30 min
Testing immediately after hot water treatment				
Seed presoaked for 3 h				
Standard germination test	+	+	+	-
Accelerated aging test	+	+	+	-
Field seedling emergence	+	+	+	-
Field seedling emergence rate	+	+	-	-
Field seedling vigor and morphological characters	++	+	+	-
Seed not presoaked				
Standard germination test	+	+	+	-
Accelerated aging test	+	+	+	-
Field seedling emergence	+	+	+	-
Field seedling emergence rate	+	+	+	-
Field seedling vigor and morphological characters	++	+	+	-
Testing after hot water treatment and 45 d storage				
Seed presoaked for 3 h				
Standard germination test	+	-	-	-
Accelerated aging test	+	+	-	-
Field seedling emergence	+	+	-	-
Field seedling emergence rate	+	+	-	-
Field seedling vigor and morphological characters	++	+	+	-
Seed not presoaked				
Standard germination test	+	+	+	-
Accelerated aging test	+	+	-	-
Field seedling emergence	+	+	+	-
Field seedling emergence rate	+	+	+	-
Field seedling vigor and morphological characters	++	+	+	-

^a + = statistically significant score reductions not observed i.e., safe treatment. ++ = scores significantly improved by the hot water treatment. - = scores significantly reduced by hot water treatment (unsafe treatment).

in vigor.

Hot water treatment of 57°C for 30 min may be considered unsafe for rice seed; the 57°C for 15 min may be considered safe only if the seed is not

presoaked before hot water treatment.

The 52°C for 15 and for 30 min treatments may be generally safe for rice seed, and are effective in controlling a range of seedborne pathogens. *S*

Genetic variability in 98 upland rice cultivars of India

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Genetic variability and extent of heritability of desirable traits were assessed in 98 upland rice cultivars sown in July 1983. Plots were 5 × 2 m in a randomized block design with 3 replications.

Range, mean, coefficients of variability, heritability, and genetic advance of 12 traits in 98 upland rice cultivars. Faizabad, India.

Trait	Range	Grand mean and SEM	GCV	PCV	ECV	Heritability (%)	Genetic advance (% of mean)
Seedling height (cm)	29.3- 67.0	51.9± 2.1	15.3	15.8	4.2	93.0	30.3
Days to 50% flowering	56.0- 99.0	77.6± 1.0	7.3	7.5	1.6	95.1	14.7
Culm angle	4.0- 27.0	12.3± 2.2	32.8	39.2	21.5	69.9	56.5
Leaf angle	9.2- 54.0	26.4± 2.4	26.7	29.0	11.4	84.5	50.4
Leaf length (cm)	31.1- 60.2	45.6± 2.9	8.9	11.9	7.9	56.2	13.7
Plant height (cm)	55.5-138.9	103.1± 3.0	14.4	14.9	3.6	94.3	28.9
Panicle length (cm)	17.4- 31.2	24.3± 1.1	9.4	10.8	5.4	75.2	16.7
Sheath length (cm)	15.8- 26.4	21.2± 1.1	6.8	9.4	6.4	52.5	10.2
Tillers/plant	5.4- 20.0	11.1± 3.1	19.5	39.3	34.1	24.7	20.0
Grains/panicle	66.0-405.6	139.0±24.3	30.7	37.5	21.4	67.3	52.0
Test weight (g)	10.4- 34.0	23.4± 1.0	15.9	16.8	5.2	90.5	31.3
Grain yield/plant (g)	5.9- 34.6	18.3± 3.2	17.2	27.7	21.7	4.0	22.1